

Characterization of bovine serum albumin adsorption onto polyethersulfone ultrafiltration membrane[†]

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Abstract : The article presents a detailed investigation of adsorption lead fouling characteristic of Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) onto Polyethersulfone (PES) ultrafiltration membrane in a standard laboratory scale cross-flow module (Viva-flow 200). Isotherms were performed to determine the equilibrium adsorption behavior; in addition to that transient adsorption rate was also determined by measuring the adsorbed mass as a function of time. The effect of different process parameters like transmembrane pressure (TMP), solution pH and feed concentration on adsorption and permeate flux has been explored under steady as well as transient condition. It was found that at pH close to the Iso-electric point of BSA, adsorbed amount reaches its maxima and hence corresponding permeate flux decreases to its minima. The equilibrium adsorption data was analyzed with nonlinear regression methods in order to determine the best suitable isotherm model amongst that of Langmuir, Freundlich and Redlich-Peterson. It was observed that Langmuir and Redlich-Peterson model can best describe the equilibrium conditions at low and high pH ranges respectively, whereas with the increase of TMP Redlich-Peterson model becomes more appropriate over that of Langmuir.

Keywords : Adsorption, cross-flow module, fouling, iso-electric point, isotherm.

1. Introduction

Flux decline during ultrafiltration of protein solution mainly occurs due to concentration polarization and membrane fouling. Concentration polarization, resulting in a localized increase in solute concentration at the membrane surface, lowers flux on account of increased hydrodynamic resistance in the boundary layer. Innovative shear-enhanced modules have been successfully proposed by various researchers^{1,2} in order to minimize the concentration polarization effect. But the problem of flux decline due to adsorption led fouling remains mostly un-addressed. Fouling problems are perhaps the single most important reason for relatively slow acceptance of ultrafiltration in chemical as well as biochemical processing. Fouling manifests itself through transient flux decline in spite of high transmembrane pressure (TMP). Depending on the specificity of the system, flux may decline in one

or more stages, usually rapid in the first few minutes followed by more gradual decline. In general it appears that membrane fouling is primarily caused by irreversible solute adsorption within the pores and onto the surface of the membrane. Irreversible adsorption produces a long-term flux decline that cannot be fully recovered by hydraulic cleaning of the membrane. Hence, an obvious consequence of fouling is higher cleaning costs. In addition, depending on the nature and extent of fouling, restoring the flux may require some powerful cleansing agents which may damage the membrane. Since fouling results lower than expected flux, effective membrane surface area need to be enhanced accordingly which incur further capital investment. Additionally it is to be noted that rejection and yield may also get affected on account of fouling. If the adsorption of solid is significant enough, it may act as a secondary membrane and change the net sieving mecha-

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

nism as well as the transport properties of the system. If the volume processed is small, the amount of solid adsorbed on the membrane is significant enough to affect the yield. Though second generation polymeric membrane like Polyethersulfone (PES) membrane is less vulnerable to fouling than cellulose acetate membrane, its effect cannot be comprehensively eliminated.

The seriousness of the fouling phenomenon impels researchers to determine the mechanisms that control fouling. Fouling analysis is difficult because the nature and extent of the solute adsorption are strongly influenced by chemical nature of the membrane and membrane-solute interaction. Convective deposition of aggregated particles, adsorption, crystallization, bio-fouling, and precipitation of small particles on the membrane surface and within the membrane pores can be important considerations. Physicochemical properties of the solute and the hydrodynamics of the membrane system also have significant effects on the solute adsorption and consequently on the membrane fouling. Due to the many phenomena occurring simultaneously at the membrane surface, a mechanistic evaluation of adsorption and fouling is a complex and elusive task. Although researchers have investigated and analyzed the characteristics of adsorption mechanisms on smooth surfaces³⁻⁵, hydrophobic membranes⁶⁻⁸ and hydrophilic membranes⁹⁻¹¹; a greater understanding of the mechanisms which control the rate and extent of irreversible membrane fouling under different solution conditions still needs to be explored. Fouling of membrane appears to be very similar in nature to the fouling of heat exchangers, at least as far food and biological fluids are concerned¹², except that the membranes have a more active surface and thus it is a more complicated phenomenon. A theoretical model was proposed by Churaev *et al.*¹³ to determine reversible adsorption inside the membrane pores and the corresponding reduction of the filtration velocity. Various researchers successfully made attempt to determine fouling mechanism for different solute-membrane combinations¹⁴⁻¹⁷. Several methods have been proposed that can minimize fouling including the change in the surface interactions between particles, change in hydrophilicity of the membrane, cleaning with agents and periodic flushing or back-flushing. In general, back-flushing is a more promising method for membrane cleaning by periodically reversing the TMP drop¹⁸. Back-flushing enables the system to operate for longer period before it is stopped for intensive physical or chemical cleaning. Furthermore, periodical back-flushing is suitable to be applied to cross-flow filtration to increase the flux.

But all the methods disrupt the continuous operation leading to a reduced productivity. Tuning of process parameter in such a level so as to reduce adsorption of solute particle at its maximum possible level is hardly available in the literature.

In contrast to the dead-end mode used mainly in laboratory tests, cross-flow mode has been actually applied in continuous operations for the separation of bio-products¹⁹. Cross-flow filtration differs from dead-end mode in that the retentate flows parallel to the membrane surface rather than normal to and toward it²⁰. Since, cross-flow limits concentration polarization effect flux decline is mainly due to fouling of the membrane. That is why, cross-flow module has been chosen for the present study which has been undertaken in an attempt to quantify the extent of Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) adsorption onto Polyethersulfone (PES) ultrafiltration membrane under different process conditions. Influences of the key factors affecting cross-flow UF performance which ultimately results into the reduction of permeate flux, such as transmembrane pressure (TMP), pH of solution and initial solute concentration have been investigated both under transient as well as steady state condition. In order to have an idea about the mechanism of adsorption, the most suitable adsorption isotherm amongst that of Langmuir, Freundlich and Redlich-Peterson has been determined by rigorous nonlinear regression analysis of the experimental data.

2. Experimental

2.1. Membrane module :

Commercially available cross-flow ultrafiltration module was used for the present study. The technical specification of Viva-flow 200 procured from Sartorius Stedin Biotech GmbH (Göttingen, Germany) has been given in Table 1. Polyethersulfone (PES) membrane with a Molecular Weight Cut-Off (MWCO) of 30 kDa was used for the experiments. The membrane module was fitted with size 16 PVC peristaltic tubing and nylon fitting as per requirement. Two pressure indicator one at the feed inlet and another at the retentate side followed by a flow restrictor were connected in order to set the transmembrane pressure (TMP) of the ultrafiltration process at desired level. Masterflex economy drive variable speed analog peristaltic pump system (Model No. HV77910-20) of 230 V was used to drive the feed solution to the module.

2.2. Chemicals and instruments :

Ultrapure analytical grade NaOH beads, NaOCl solu-

Table 1. Technical specification of membrane module

1. Module dimension	
Overall Length Height Width	26 138 38 mm
Channel width Height	10 0.4 mm
Active membrane area	200 cm ²
Hold up volume	5.3 ml
Non recoverable hold up	< 2 ml
2. Material of construction	
Membrane housing	Acrylic fibre
Flow channel	Acrylic fibre
Membrane support	Polypropylene
Seals	Silicon
Pressure indicator	Polypropylene, stainless steel spring
Flow restrictor	Polypropylene
Tube fittings	Nylon
Tubing	PVC
3. Operating condition	
Maximum fluid flow	400 ml/min
Maximum pressure drop	400 kPa
Maximum operating temperature	608 °C

tion and ethanol were procured from Merck, India. 10% (v/v) ethanol solution was used for membrane storage under refrigeration. Crystalline Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) was procured from Sigma Aldrich (Product No. A2934). BSA is an ellipsoid protein (negatively charged in neutral aqueous solution) with dimension of 14 × 4 nm and average molecular weight of 67 kDa²¹. The iso-

electric point of BSA solution has been reported to be 4.7 in literature²². Laboratory grade 1 (N) HCl was purchased from Stanbio Reagent (P) Ltd, Kolkata, India. 1 (N) NaOH and HCl solution were required to set the pH of feed solution at desired level. Ultrapure water for various purposes was obtained from an ultrapure water system (Arium 611 DI Ultrapure water system) of Sartorius-AG, Göttingen, Germany.

Concentration of BSA solution was measured spectrophotometrically at a wavelength of 280 nm. A programmable UV-Visible spectrophotometer (Lamda 25. Perkin-Elmer) was used for the purpose. pH of BSA solution was measured with a digital pH meter purchased from Systronix. Digital weighing machine procured from Sartorius was used for various measuring purpose.

2.3. Experimental procedure :

2.3.1. Membrane compaction and water run :

Prior to the use in experiments each membrane module was subjected to compaction for about 1 h with ultrapure water at a pressure of 300 kPa, higher than the highest operating pressure used in this study in order to prevent the variation of hydraulic resistance (R_m) during ultrafiltration. Once the water flux became steady with no further decrease it was concluded that full compaction of membrane was achieved. After compaction, membrane hydraulic resistance was determined based on water runs at different TMPs of 100, 150, 200, 250 and 300 kPa.

2.3.2. Filtration operation :

The cross-flow ultrafiltration experiments were conducted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The schematic experimental setup for cross-flow UF process.

Each experiment was performed at 25 °C in an air conditioned chamber. The cross-flow velocity and TMP were adjusted by peristaltic pump fitted with an rpm controller. Because the system was equipped with two pressure gauges (one at the upstream of inlet to the membrane and another at the downstream) the TMP of the system was calculated as

$$\text{TMP} = \left(\frac{P_{\text{in}} + P_{\text{out}}}{2} \right) - P_{\text{pm}} \quad (1)$$

where, P_{in} , P_{out} and P_{pm} are the pressure in the feed, retentate and permeate respectively (kPa). The pressure at the permeate side, P_{pm} was considered to be one atmospheric pressure i.e. 101 kPa.

The cross-flow ultrafiltration experiment was conducted by varying three different adjustable process parameters : TMP (150, 175, 200 kPa), pH (2.5, 4.71 and 6.5) and initial solute concentration (0.05, 0.15, 0.25 and 0.35 kg m⁻³). Five liters of BSA solution of desired concentration was first prepared. The pH of the solution was then adjusted at desired level by adding 0.1 (N) HCl or 0.1 (N) freshly prepared NaOH solutions as per requirement followed by vigorous stirring in a mixing tank. The pH of the solution was continuously monitored by a digital pH meter. The variation of BSA concentration due to addition of very minute quantity of HCl or NaOH solution was found to be more or less 0.1 %, which was negligibly small. The salt concentration on account of adding HCl and NaOH was also negligible.

Feed solution thus prepared was then pumped to the membrane module at a desired TMP with retentate recycled back to the feed tank. The permeate flux was measured gravimetrically with an electronic balance by continuously weighing the permeate, which was collected in permeate tank. The filtration operation was carried out until the flux became steady. On achieving steady permeate flux, BSA concentration was measured at both permeate and retentate side.

2.3.3. Membrane cleaning and its reuse :

After each experimental run membrane module was cleaned thoroughly with a suitable cleaning agent (250 ml of 0.5 mM NaOCl in 0.5 M NaOH solution) according to the protocol shown in Fig. 2 to minimize irreversible membrane fouling so that it could be reused. If the

variation in R_m after experimental run and subsequent chemical cleaning was not more than 0.5% then only the module was reused further considering R_m to be more or less constant otherwise it was replaced with a new one of exactly identical configuration.

3. Results and discussion

The extent of adsorption on membrane and permeate flux of BSA solution was measured at a uniform time interval until the steady state condition was achieved for different parametric condition of cross-flow UF process. The adsorbed amount of BSA was determined by measuring concentration of BSA in the feed tank and permeate tank over the same uniform time interval. Hence, BSA adsorbed per unit of membrane surface area is given as

$$Y_t = \frac{1}{A_m} \left[V_0 C_0 - \{ V_{\text{pt}} C_{\text{pt}} + (V_0 - V_{\text{pt}}) C_{\text{ft}} \} \right] \quad (2)$$

The permeate flux at time t i.e. J_t , can be obtained from the slope of the tangent drawn on the time of cumulative permeate volume, V_{pt} versus time plot. Then the permeate flux at any point of time is determined as

$$J_{t=t_1} = \frac{1}{A_m} \left(\frac{dV_{\text{pt}}}{dt} \right)_{t=t_1} \quad (3)$$

In the following sections, the effect of different process variables like transmembrane pressure (TMP), pH of solution and initial bulk concentration (C_0) on permeate flux and adsorption during both transient and steady state condition has been thoroughly analyzed.

3.1. Transient behavior of permeate flux and adsorption :

The transient permeate flux and adsorption at different parametric conditions has been shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4. It is seen from the figures that the adsorption and permeate flux exhibits a mutually opposite trend during the transient quasi-equilibrium condition as stated by Salehi and Madaeni²³. As the adsorption increases the corresponding permeate flux decreases and as soon as permeate flux reaches its steady state adsorption on the other hand achieves equilibrium. This may be due to the fact that as the solute molecule adsorb gradually within the pores, effective diameter decreases that results into a reduced permeate flux at constant TMP. It is observed from the

Fig. 2. Cross-flow module operation and membrane cleaning protocol.

Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 that the rate of change of flux as well as adsorbed amount are initially very fast then decreases gradually and subsequently levels off as the steady state condition is reached. The time to reach equilibrium is found to be dependent on solution pH and TMP. The fastest equilibrium (within 40 min) was observed at TMP 150 kPa and pH 6.5 and the slowest one (within 55 min) was at TMP 200 kPa and pH 4.71. The maximum delay in reaching equilibrium was noticed for the solution pH of 4.71 which is the iso-electric point (IEP) of BSA. This is perhaps because the number of potential adsorption

sites on the membrane surface and pores on account of neutral behavior of adsorbate at IEP is very large which require more time to get saturated. It is also to be noted that equilibrium can be delayed on increasing TMP keeping all other parameter constant. This is may be due to slowing down the adsorption kinetics at higher TMP on account of higher velocity of fluid through membrane pore. Another fact is to be noticed from the Fig. 3 that initial permeate flux is independent of bulk concentration and solution pH but only depends on TMP because initially the membrane surface and pores are free of adsorbed solute.

Fig. 3. Variation of permeate flux as a function of time for different trans-membrane pressure drop (TMP), and initial feed concentration (C_0) at constant solution pH (4.71) [Inset : transient behavior of permeate flux at different pH at constant TMP (175 kPa) and C_0 (0.15 kg m^{-3})].

Fig. 4. Variation of adsorption of BSA over membrane as a function of time for different trans-membrane pressure drop (TMP), pH at constant initial feed concentration ($C_0 = 0.15 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$).

3.2. Effect of TMP on steady permeate flux and equilibrium adsorption :

Fig. 5 shows the steady state permeate flux profile

with TMP at different initial solute concentration and solution pH. It is noted from the figure that with increasing TMP steady state permeate flux increases almost lin-

early as expected and the rate of increase of flux with respect to TMP does not vary appreciably with the change of other parameters, namely the pH and initial concentration. The rate of increase of flux with respect to TMP is found to be maximum ($2.03 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$) for pH

4.71 with C_0 at 0.35 kg m^{-3} and minimum ($1.72 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$) for pH 6.5 with C_0 at 0.05 kg m^{-3}

The effect of TMP on steady state adsorption of BSA per unit membrane surface area has been shown in Fig. 6. An increasing trend similar to permeate flux is

Fig. 5. Variation of steady state permeate flux as a function of TMP for different solution pH and initial feed concentration

Fig. 6. Variation of equilibrium adsorption as a function of TMP for different solution pH and initial feed concentration

observed keeping other two parameters unaltered. This is probably due to the fact that at higher TMP, BSA macromolecule with reduced effective coil size can penetrate into the porous membrane more easily and get adsorbed on the inner surface of pores enhancing the degree of adsorption. Another thing is to be noticed from Fig. 6 that at higher C_0 the rate of change of adsorption with TMP is very low on account of non availability of vacant adsorption site on membrane. On the other hand, at lower C_0 , adsorption increases appreciably with increase in TMP. This is revealed from the fact that at pH 4.71 and $C_0 = 0.35 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ adsorption of BSA per unit membrane surface is increased only by 3.37% while 46.3% increase of the same is recorded for pH 2.5 and $C_0 = 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ with increase in TMP from 175 to 200 kPa.

The reason of increasing permeate flux in relation to the increased adsorbed amount with increasing TMP can be explained as follows. If the porous structure of membrane can be considered as packed bed filled with adsorbed BSA macromolecule then with the increase in TMP permeate flux should increase according to Ergun equation²⁴. But on the other hand, with increase in TMP void fraction of the bed decreases on account of higher adsorption which causes a reducing effect to permeate flux. Since permeate flux is found to be increasing with TMP it may be concluded qualitatively that reducing effect on permeate flux due to increased adsorption can only cut short a certain fraction of enhancing effect of permeate flux due to increased TMP.

3.3. Effect of pH on steady permeate flux and equilibrium adsorption :

In present study, cross-flow UF experiments were carried out at three different pH, one below IEP of BSA i.e. at 2.5, one above IEP i.e. at 6.5 and another at IEP i.e. at 4.71. Fig. 7 shows the variation of steady permeate flux as a function of pH for different TMP and initial feed concentration. It can be clearly observed from the figure that each and every curve that represents different TMP and C_0 passes through minima at pH same as the IEP of BSA. Though permeate flux increases on both side of IEP, it is further noticed that rate of increase of flux is somewhat higher on decreasing acid strength of solution. The extent of permeate flux enhancement on either side of IEP is found to be influenced by other two

parameter (TMP and C_0) also. It is observed from experimentation that the effect of pH on permeate flux is much more pronounced at low TMP and more dilute initial feed concentration. This can be established from the fact that steady permeate flux increases only by 5.1% on decreasing pH from 4.71 to 2.5 at TMP 200 kPa and $C_0 0.35 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ whereas flux increases by 13.4% at TMP 150 kPa and $C_0 0.05 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ for identical changes in pH.

Variation of equilibrium BSA adsorption with pH has been depicted in Fig. 8 at different TMP and initial feed concentration. The qualitative nature of curves as shown in Fig. 8 is just the opposite of the trend as obtained in Fig. 7 i.e. adsorption was found to be maximum at pH same as the IEP over the entire range of other two parameters, namely the TMP and C_0 . Adsorption decreases more rapidly by increasing pH and vice-versa. Just like permeate flux, variation of adsorption with pH is immensely influenced by TMP and C_0 . On reducing pH from 4.71 to 2.5, adsorption decreases by 20.3% at higher side value of TMP and C_0 (200 kPa and 0.35 kg m^{-3}) while 42.7% reduction in adsorption is recorded at lower side value of TMP and C_0 (150 kPa and 0.05 kg m^{-3}).

From the above discussion it may be inferred that with pH deviant from the iso-electric point of BSA permeate flux increases on account of reduced BSA adsorption. Actually the interaction of BSA with PES membrane is a function of solution pH. Böhme and Scheler²⁵ showed that the effective charge of BSA in aqueous solution results from degree of dissociation that varies with pH and local counter ion concentration. At IEP, BSA exhibits a neutral behavior. At solution pH above IEP, BSA behaves as negatively charged species while below IEP it is positively charged. From streaming potential measurement²⁶, IEP of PES membrane of 30 kDa MWCO is reported to be 2.38. Hence, at pH 2.5 positively charged BSA molecules interact with almost neutral membrane resulting into reduced adsorption due to electrostatic repulsive action. On the other hand, at pH 6.5 negatively charged BSA molecule interacts with slight negatively charged (on account of negligible salt concentration) membrane. This causes further less adsorption due to simultaneous repulsive force experienced by the neighboring molecule and membrane surface. In spite of neutral behavior of BSA molecule at pH 4.71 a weak electrostatic

Fig. 7. Variation of steady state permeate flux with pH for different TMP and initial feed concentration.

Fig. 8. Variation of equilibrium adsorption with pH for different TMP and initial feed concentration.

attractive force generates due to induction effect between molecule and membrane surface resulting into maximum adsorption.

3.4. Adsorption isotherm :

The solution phase in contact with the membrane is assumed to be in equilibrium with the surface phase com-

posed to adsorbed BSA. Since polarization induced concentration gradient is negligibly small in a standard laboratory scale cross-flow module, the retentate concentration is assumed to be same as the membrane surface concentration. Accordingly the average solute concentration across the membrane under steady state condition may be assumed to be same as the log-mean²⁷ of the permeate and the retentate concentrations as

$$C_m = \left(\frac{C_R - C_p}{\ln \frac{C_R}{C_p}} \right) \quad (4)$$

Accordingly for isotherm study the average solute concentration (C_m) is used as equilibrium concentration in testing the applicability of standard isotherms like Langmuir and Freundlich whereas the steady state adsorbed solute per unit membrane surface area (Y_{st}) has been considered as the equilibrium adsorbed amount or equilibrium solid concentration.

The well known Langmuir adsorption isotherm²⁸ that assumes monolayer adsorption can be directly applied for solute-membrane system as

$$Y_{st} = \frac{aC_m}{1 + bC_m} \quad (5)$$

where, Y_{st} is the equilibrium adsorbed amount per unit membrane surface and a , b are the two isotherm constants.

The empirical Freundlich isotherm²⁹ describes multilayer adsorption with interaction between molecules and membrane surface, which can be represented as

$$Y_{st} = kC_m^{1/n} \quad (6)$$

where, k and n are the constant that represent relative adsorption capacity and an indicator of surface heterogeneity respectively.

Redlich-Peterson is a three parameter empirical isotherm model^{28,29}, which can be used to represent adsorption equilibrium over a wide range of concentrations both for homogeneous as well as heterogeneous systems. This isotherm also considers lateral interaction between the adsorbed solute molecules and is represented as

$$Y_{st} = \frac{a'C_m}{b' + C_m^{c'}} \quad (7)$$

where, a' and b' are the isotherm constant and c' is an exponent which indicates heterogeneity of the adsorbing surface.

Three adsorption isotherms, i.e. Langmuir, Freundlich, and Redlich-Peterson are applied to fit the equilibrium adsorption data for different parametric conditions (TMP and pH). The best fitted isotherm is determined comparing the reduced chi-square values for a given operating condition as shown in Table 2. The corresponding isotherm constants have also been provided in the table. It is seen from the table that with varying operating condition, mainly pH of solution, best fit isotherm changes from one to another, which implies that the mechanism of solute-membrane interaction pattern changes with the change of parametric conditions for the present system. It is found from regression analysis that Langmuir isotherm is being followed by the present system at pH 4.71 over the entire range of TMP. This is probably because, at the IEP, lateral interaction between neighboring adsorbed solute molecules is very unlikely on account of neutral behavior of BSA molecule that promotes monolayer adsorption on membrane. At pH less than IEP, because of the developed positive charge on BSA molecule electrostatic repulsion generates lateral interaction between absorbing species, which probably causes Redlich-Peterson isotherm to be the best fit at pH 2.5 over the entire TMP range. But it is to be noted that at pH higher than IEP, adsorption isotherm is found to be dependent on TMP. As stated earlier, electrostatic repulsion between membrane and adsorbate reduces the degree of adsorption. At low TMP, majority of the adsorption site is vacant and hence lateral interaction is very much improbable. Due to intermolecular electrostatic repulsion multilayer adsorption may also become less probable that paves the way for Langmuir isotherm to be the best fit at pH 6.5 and at low TMP (150 kPa). At higher TMP (175 kPa, 200 kPa), some of the vacant sites get occupied by BSA molecule resulting into lateral repulsive interaction between neighboring species that causes Redlich-Peterson isotherm to become the most suitable one for the present system at pH 6.5.

In order to be more informative about the nature of

Table 2. Best fitted adsorption isotherm for different operating conditions with corresponding adsorption constant

Operating condition		Reduced chi-square (χ^2) values	Best fitted adsorption isotherm	Isotherm constants (SI system)
TMP (kPa)	pH			
150	2.5	Langmuir model : 2.379×10^{-10}	Redlich-Peterson model	$a' = 1$
		Freundlich model : 9.8175×10^{-11}		$b' = 147.2857$
		Redlich-Peterson model : 6.296×10^{-11}		$c' = -1.66324$
	4.71	Langmuir model : 9.489×10^{-11}	Langmuir model	$a = 0.00383$
		Freundlich model : 9.656×10^{-11}		$b = 1.88077$
		Redlich-Peterson model : 9.544×10^{-11}		
	6.5	Langmuir model : 2.233×10^{-11}	Langmuir model	$a = 0.00155$
		Freundlich model : 3.524×10^{-11}		$b = -3.15673$
		Redlich-Peterson model : 5.208×10^{-11}		
175	2.5	Langmuir model : 5.923×10^{-10}	Redlich-Peterson model	$a' = 1$
		Freundlich model : 4.702×10^{-10}		$b' = 212.4163$
		Redlich-Peterson model : 2.526×10^{-10}		$c' = -1.47127$
	4.71	Langmuir model : 8.698×10^{-11}	Langmuir model	$a = 0.00325$
		Freundlich model : 8.9533×10^{-11}		$b = -0.6997$
		Redlich-Peterson model : 1.8779×10^{-10}		
	6.5	Langmuir model : 3.3202×10^{-10}	Redlich-Peterson model	$a' = 0.30722$
		Freundlich model : 2.604×10^{-10}		$b' = 71.82122$
		Redlich-Peterson model : 2.132×10^{-10}		$c' = -1.0896$
2.5	Langmuir model : 2.663×10^{-10}	Redlich-Peterson model	$a' = 1$	
	Freundlich model : 2.204×10^{-10}		$b' = 260.46$	
	Redlich-Peterson model : 1.7315×10^{-10}		$c' = -1.31677$	
200	4.71	Langmuir model : 2.663×10^{-10}	Langmuir model	$a = 0.00301$
		Freundlich model : 2.204×10^{-10}		$b = -1.83008$
		Redlich-Peterson model : 1.7315×10^{-10}		
	6.5	Langmuir model : 3.1278×10^{-10}	Redlich-Peterson model	$a' = 1.00114$
		Freundlich model : 2.467×10^{-10}		$b' = 245.06611$
		Redlich-Peterson model : 1.2327×10^{-10}		$c' = -1.4139$

adsorption, different isotherm constants have been plotted as a function of TMP at a given pH as shown in Figs. 9 and 10. From Fig. 9, it is seen that, the quantity a/b (defined in eq. 5) which signifies the maximum adsorption capacity at a given operating condition increases with TMP but inset shows that the quantity b , which reflects affinity of membrane for adsorbate decreases with increasing TMP at pH 4.71. From Fig. 10, it is seen that the exponent of Redlich-Peterson isotherm, the quantity c' (as defined in eq. 7) that indicates surface heterogeneity increases with increasing TMP. At higher TMP, membrane surface becomes more and more heterogeneous because of multilayer adsorption.

4. Conclusion

Absorption characteristic of BSA onto PES membrane and the permeate flux behavior are thoroughly investigated at various operating conditions during ultrafiltration in a standard cross flow module. It is found that permeate flux first reduces sharply then gradually and ultimately levels off to a steady state value due to partial blockage of membrane pore caused by solute adsorption. Hence, as adsorption intensifies permeate flux reduces. But TMP is found to impart a similar effect on flux and adsorption i.e. on increasing TMP adsorption and flux both increases simultaneously keeping other parameter constant. pH of solution has a profound effect on adsorp-

Fig. 9. Langmuir adsorption constant (a/b as defined in eq. 5) as a function of TMP at pH 4.71 [Inset : Variation of b (as defined in eq 4) as a function of TMP at pH 4.71].

Fig. 10. Redlich-Peterson adsorption constant (c' as defined in eq. 5) as a function of TMP at pH 2.5.

tion characteristic and hence permeate flux because of electrostatic interaction between membrane and adsorbate. At pH equal to IEP of BSA adsorption is maximum and corresponding permeate flux is minimum at a given operating condition. Adsorption decreases more rapidly

with increasing pH from IEP of BSA solution than vice-versa. Higher initial feed concentration is found to enhance adsorption and hence reduces permeate flux, although initial permeate flux is independent of feed concentration and solution pH. Transient behavior of ad-

sorption and flux show that achievement of equilibrium can be advanced on decreasing TMP at a pH deviant from the iso-electric point of the solute.

Adsorption equilibrium isotherm is investigated for different operating condition. Both Langmuir and Redlich-Peterson isotherm conveniently describe the equilibrium data. At IEP of BSA, Langmuir adsorption isotherm is found to follow that reflects mono-layer adsorption with minimum lateral interaction between neutral adsorbing species. On deviating pH from either side of IEP Redlich-Peterson adsorption is mainly followed on account electrostatic repulsion of charged molecular species. At pH 6.5, adsorption isotherm gets shifted from Langmuir to Redlich-Peterson on increasing TMP.

Notations

A_m	Active membrane surface area (m^2)
a	Langmuir adsorption isotherm parameter as defined in eq. (5)
a'	Redlich-Peterson adsorption isotherm parameter as defined in eq. (7)
BSA	Bovine Serum Albumin
b	Langmuir adsorption isotherm constant as defined in eq. (5)
b'	Redlich-Peterson adsorption isotherm parameter as defined in eq. (7)
C_0	Initial feed concentration ($kg\ m^{-3}$)
C_{tt}	Solute concentration of feed tank at any time, t ($kg\ m^{-3}$)
C_m	Concentration of solute across membrane as defined in eq. (4) ($kg\ m^{-3}$)
C_p	Steady state permeate solute concentration ($kg\ m^{-3}$)
C_{pt}	Solute concentration of permeate tank at any time, t ($kg\ m^{-3}$)
C_R	Steady state retentate solute concentration ($kg\ m^{-3}$)
c'	Redlich-Peterson adsorption isotherm parameter as defined in eq. (7)
IEP	Iso-electric point
J	Steady state volumetric permeate flux ($m^3\ m^{-2}\ s^{-1}$)
J_t	Volumetric permeate flux at any time, t ($m^3\ m^{-2}\ s^{-1}$)
k	Freundlich adsorption isotherm parameter as defined in eq. (6)
MWCO	Molecular Weight Cut-Off
P_{in}	Pressure at the inlet of feed stream (kPa)
P_{out}	Pressure at the outlet of retentate side (kPa)

P_{pm}	Pressure at the outlet of permeate side (kPa)
R_m	Membrane hydraulic resistance (m^{-1})
TMP	Transmembrane pressure (kPa)
t	Time (s)
V_0	Initial feed solution volume (m^3)
V_{pt}	Cumulative volume of solution in permeate tank at any time, t (m^3)
Y_{st}	Steady state adsorption per unit membrane surface area ($kg\ m^{-2}$)
Y_t	Adsorption per unit membrane surface area at any time, t ($kg\ m^{-2}$)

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